

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND HEALTH EFFECTS OF PEDOPHILIA ON ADOLESCENTS

JIMOH, Biliqis Mosunmola

Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria.
E-mail: jimohbiliqis206@gmail.com

ENIOLA Lateefat Motunrayo

Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria.
E-mail: eniolamotunrayolateefat@gmail.com

&

ZAKARIYAH Fatimat Fadeke

Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria.
E-mail: fatimatzakariyah@gmail.com

Abstract

Pedophilia, a form of sexual perversion is now one of the famous socio-health and psychological issues in human society. It has recently gained prominence, raising serious concerns among scholars, researchers and health work professionals as well as counsellors trying to find lasting means of curbing this behavioural maladjustment in human society as it always leaves both serious short and long-term psychological, health, and emotional and physical effects on the victims and the society at large to romance with. This paper therefore reviews pedophilia as a concept about its effects on adolescents specifically and the society at large after uncovering some of its causes. Exploratory research method where diverse recent cases of pedophilia reported by various Nigerian news, published articles and other research databases were explored as methods of data source for this study. The paper also presents some possible ways through which this undesirable behaviour can be prevented or reduced to the barest minimum if not phased off in society through its recommendations.

Key Words: Pedophilia, Pedophile, Psychological effects, Health effects and Adolescents

Introduction

The rate of moral decadence and bankruptcy in contemporary human society has assumed preponderance to the extent that society has been rubbed off of its ideals. Sexual behaviours that were once seen as secret or room affairs are now been displayed freely without conscience even at the market square. Girl children mostly adolescents have dishearteningly lost safety in the supposed custody of their uncle, cousin, brother, teacher and even father when it comes to gratification of sexual

urges. Some people do not pay homage to paternal or maternal ties again; they stand to consume all that their net caught. They could not differentiate between a blood relationship and a nuptial relationship not to mention the age disparity that validates an ideal sexual relationship between two opposite individuals. This attitude of having sex with a girl child who is still minor or underage is termed pedophilia. It is a form of sexual assault, sexual molestation or child sexual abuse.

Pedophilia as a Concept

Seto (2018) opined that pedophilia is a derivative of the Greek word “philia pedeiktos” meaning erotic love of children. It includes using children as a sexual excitement object to reach gratification. Esra and Nesin (2018) stressed that in most cultures, children are not deemed as mature enough to make decisions about sexual intercourse. In this regard, child sexual abuse is not only intolerable but is also sanctioned in many societies. However, the alarming rate of its prevalence in society today spurs the researcher to investigate its causes and aftermaths on adolescents.

Pedophilia is a kind of sexual pleasure and passion or attraction that occurs due to fantasizing and unusual behaviour. Zeljko (2020) stressed that not all forms of attraction are paraphilias; they become it only when it is the only way of achieving sexual satisfaction. In persons who exhibit such behaviour, obsessive sexual needs and fantasies that cause significant hindrance or inadequacies in social, work and living surroundings are dominating (Zeljko, 2020).

Pedophilia as a sexual behavioural disorder that is directed towards a pre-age, minor, preadolescent or prepubescent has become an issue of daily occurrence in human society taking different forms ranging from physical to online perpetration questioning the wellness of the human mind. Doshi, Zanzrukiya and Kumar (2018) subscribed that pedophilia refers to the state of adults being sexually interested in children, it is an inclination in adults to have sex with a child, and a person has pedophilia if he has relatively frequent and intense pedophilic desire. Lo Lanco, Trentini and Carola (2021) submitted that pedophilia entails intercourse, attempted intercourse or oral-genital contact with the penis, fingers or any object; masturbation and fondling the genital or another erogenous area.

Pedophilia is a form of paraphilias recognized and classified in the DSM-V (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder, V. ed) stated that for child sexual molestation to be considered pedophilia, it must meet these criteria: recurring sexual fantasies, impulses or behaviours involving one or more prepubertal children (usually thirteen (13) years) that have been present for not less than six months; the person is driven by the impulse, has difficulty resisting the impulses or is altered by the impulses and fantasies and the person is not less than sixteen years old and at least five years older than the child-targeted by the fantasies or behaviour (Perrotta, 2019). Pedophilia which is also spelled as peadophilia is as well-known as a pedophilic disorder, generally affecting adults, characterized by sexual interest in prepubescent children or attempts to engage in sexual acts with prepubescent children.

It can be inferred from the above that pedophilia based on psychology is a sort of feeling in which adults have and nurse sexual interest in minors of either or both sexes. It should be mentioned here that whether the feeling or interest is acted upon or not, it is still a social vice and it is an unacceptable behaviour. It should be stressed here also that pedophilia is a form of sexual abuse that is directed towards underage. This sexual abuse is also known or referred to as molestation or assault (Kawamoto, 2013 & Seto, 2019). Child sexual abuse or molestation is a form of child abuse that includes sexual activity with a prepubertal child. This action does not necessarily have to be in the form of physical contact; it can include digital interactions; exhibitionism; pornographic material containing children; and any other sexual conduct that is harmful to a child’s mental, emotional or physical welfare (Heather & Caccitori, 2017: 11).

World Health Organization (2010) is quoted by Perrotta (2020) to have stressed that child sexual abuse is the involvement of a child in sexual activity that he or she cannot fully comprehend. Child sexual abuse is evidenced by this activity between a child and an adult or another child who by age or development is in a relationship of responsibility, trust, or power. The said activity is intended to gratify or satisfy the needs of the other person. This may include but not limited to:

- The inducement or coercion of a child to engage in any unlawful sexual activity
- The exploitative use of children in prostitution or other unlawful sexual practices
- The exploitative use of children in pornographic performances and materials (Karoline, 2018).

From the foregoing, it becomes crystal clear that pedophilia is a sort of sexual disorder that is driven towards children. The attitude is socially unacceptable whether it has been acted upon or it remains a wish. Merely nursing the feeling or interest to have sex with a child is considered taboo and is seriously frowned upon socially in all human society. An individual with this type of feeling or disorder is seen as an animal in human skin and is always stigmatized.

It is important to note that, while pedophile prefers to have sex with children, they can and do have sex with adults. Seto (2004) noted that adult sexual relationships are more difficult for some pedophiles than for others. The researcher further stated that some pedophiles have sex with adults as part of their efforts to gain or continue their access to preferred children as one might have occasional sex with a single mother to ensure continued access to her children. The illustration of this is the case of a comedian and an actor who

had been in a friendship relationship with the foster mother of his victim. The accused had been paying his friend visits only to gain access to his target victim for almost seven years as disclosed in the court (Ripples Nigeria, 2022).

A person suffering from paraphilia can legally engage in it simply by fantasizing or masturbating. Some pedophiles might act out their fantasies by talking to or watching children and later masturbating; some might have sex with dolls or mannequins that resemble children, some may even act out their fantasies by engaging in sexual activity with adults who look (small stature, flat chest, no body hair), dress or act (immature, baby talk) like children or act out child fantasy games with adult prostitutes (Seto, 2004; 2009 & Kawamoto, 2013).

It should be stressed at this juncture that pedophiles do not use force to have sex with a child instead they tend to place themselves in a position where they can interact with a child in an unsupervised environment such as being a babysitter, sports coach, teacher, care-giver or step-parent. It is rare, but when force is applied in a sexual assault, approximately 70% of child victims do not know the offender (Cohen & Galyner, 2002).

To buttress the above fact is the case of pedophilia that took place in a city in Osun state as reported by Faturoti (2021), where the pedophile is said to have been visiting the house of the child victim and the parents did not suspect him in any way because of the way he always interacted with them. On the fateful day of his exposure, the victim, a ten-year-old girl narrated. "He visited our house and sent my siblings who were chuckling in an array of excitement outside on an errand. Not long after, he dragged me to our

veranda while I screamed in defiance. With fierce eyes and threats to kill me, he grappled my neck by the jugular and forcefully had carnal knowledge of me” (Faturoti, 2021).

It is pertinent to mention at this juncture that the majority of the victims of pedophilia are people in the adolescence stage of development. Adolescence is the period of life between childhood and adulthood. Typically, adolescence begins with the onset of puberty which technically refers to the time at which an individual is first able to reproduce (Adegoke, 2016). Adolescence is one of the most fascinating and complex transitions in an individual’s life span: a time of accelerated growth and change second only to infancy, a time of expanding horizons, self-discovery and emerging interdependence; a time of metamorphosis from childhood to adulthood (Adegoke, 2016). In number, the age or period of adolescence is generally between age ten (10) and twenty-one (21) (Adegoke, 2016, Ajagbe & Adekale, 2014). The period has three phases which are early adolescence, middle adolescence, and late adolescence. Early adolescence encompasses the sexual and psychological awakening of puberty as well as new social challenges. This period extends from ages ten through fourteen; middle adolescence is a time of increased autonomy and experimentation and it covers roughly from age fifteen through seventeen while late adolescence occurs for those who delay their entry into adult roles because of educational or social factors and their stage can stretch from age eighteen into the early twenties.

Considering the discourse of this paper, early adolescence which involves the sexual, physiological and psychological awakening of puberty is

much focused as most of the victims fall within this stage of development. Puberty from a medical perspective is the period of physical growth leading to the attainment of reproductive capability (Brooks-Gum & Peterson, 1983 in Adegoke, 2016). Adekale and Ajagbe (2014) stated that puberty refers to the time when reproductive organs mature and begin to function. The period of puberty is notably divided into three which are Pre-pubescence, Pubescence and Post-pubescence. Pre-pubescence stage which has much bearing with pedophilia is an immature stage when bodily changes are taking place and when the secondary sex characteristics are just beginning to show but the reproductive function is yet to develop well (Adekale & Ajagbe, 2014).

However, adolescents who are individuals who are in the state of development between puberty and maturity are described by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2014) as those people between 10 and 19 years of age. The great majority of adolescents are therefore included in the age-based definition of “child”, (WHO, 2014). From this description, we see that these sets of individuals are still undergoing development which is very crucial to their healthy living and should not be tampered with in any form and if this is done, it will leave an indelible dent in all spheres of their lives at the moment and in the later part of their lives. Sigmund Freud in his psychoanalytic theory stressed that the experiences one has at childhood stage speak louder at his adulthood stage (Alutu, 2017; Abiola, 2006). It then follows that if a girl child is sexually abused during these formative years, there is every propensity that such survivor would grow to nurse adverse effects of pedophilia such as

depression, anxiety, and sexual misbehaviours to mention but a few. With this, it becomes imperative to stress that pedophilia disorder/pedophiliac behaviour should be checked, prevented or if possible, forced out in society because of its harmful and destructive effects on the personality development of its victim both at present and in the future.

Causes of Pedophilia

An individual is a product of both nature and nurture. The environment where one hails from makes or mars one's personality and way of life. Pedophilia as a sexually deviant behaviour can be a product of one's social environment. Among the most obvious examples of environmental factors that increase the chances of an individual becoming an offender or a victim are:

Relationship between parents and children:

- Inadequate or poor relationships between children and parents lead to weak and insecure attachment between parents and children. A weak bond between parent and child influences the child making her seek relationships with other adults, to compensate for this poor attachment (Seto, 2002; Bahroo, 2005). This new parent in most cases tries to build a loving bond by showering on targeted minors in this condition gifts which would make these minors have trust in them thinking that they are safe. This category of pseudo-parent is known as playful pedophile in the language of Perrotta (2020) who claimed that playful pedophile tends to play with children and rarely traumatize them. The game has the dual purpose of winning the trust of the parents and the child and of setting an attitude of silence with the child, proposed as part of the game itself.

However, when children are not shown the desired love and care, they tend to look for substitutes where at least they

can be shown love and care temporarily, the opportunity which some people have and nursing this deviant sexual behaviour tap to successfully perpetrate such heinous behaviour. This is in line with the findings of Oluwatosin and Akinbo (2017).

Parental carelessness and irresponsibility:

- Relating to the above is parental carelessness and irresponsibility. Agbo (2019) stressed that many parents due to their quest for money or tight office work feel that bombarding their children with foodstuff and other luxuries is always the best for the kids. Such parents abandon their little children early in the morning at the mercy of yard members or even without anybody to guard them, and come back late in the night. In such situations, children are denied love, affection, close monitoring and guidance. The children become their mothers, loitering around without restrictions or being monitored. These attitudes expose young adolescents to all sorts of dangers and specifically pedophilia (Oluwatosin & Akinbo, 2017; Agbo, 2019).

Exposure to social media: - Another popular cause of pedophilia in our society today is the unbridled exposure to social media. Everything on earth is like a coin with two sides, the head and the tail, positive and negative, social media is not left out of two sides of positive and negative. However, social media of its positive side has been the reflection of technological advancement and globalization of the communication industry but has dishearteningly destroyed our moral values, its negative side. It has become a dumping site where everything and all things are dumped without censure in respect of our existing moral values and uprightness of humanity.

The rate at which our younger generation has been exposed to media is no doubt a strong contributor to social vices of which pedophilia is one. In a situation

where minors are seen having Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram accounts and the likes, what are they looking for, are these educational websites on the media? There is no how they would be operating these without being exposed to sexualities that are not congruent with their age and this would be pushing them to experiment with what they have been seeing, watching or reading about. In the same vein, online pedophiles would have ample opportunity to make online baiting attempts on their target victims.

Among numerous cases exposed and unexposed is the recent case of Chrisland School where a ten-year-old girl went on her Instagram page to stir the whole world that she was raped as she called it by her school mate who is also a minor. Going by the posts of the girl in question, she has been posting untold outrageous pictures, and videos, and displaying erotic and romantic dancing steps which were all recorded under the roof of her parents. The Facebook record has it that she has posted over 526 videos with 4,134 followers as of Easter Monday in the year 2022 (Facebook, April 2022).

To be candid, there is no how one would be watching or reading about this type of post that one as a human being with a sound sexual system would not want to have the real experience of it. It thus amounts to inviting the predator and it should be noted that this is just one out of thousands of posters. However, being prepubescent or pubescent does not make one unattractive, to admirers; thus, being online underage exposes them to the danger of being pedophilia victims.

Access to Pornography: - Closely related to the above is the issue of pornography-movies, pictures, books and magazines that show or describe naked people or sex in a very open and direct way to cause sexual excitement (Merriam-Webster, 2023). Children who are addicted to online would

surely be exposed to pornography indiscriminately. This invariably would be grooming them towards promiscuity which can make them become pedophilia victims especially when a grown-up introduces them to pornography being one of the techniques pedophiles employ to entice their victims. Perrotta (2020) stressed that in recent years; the internet has become another place (albeit non-physical) where potential victims may be found, thanks to social networks and online messaging.

Strano (2003) stated that online pedophiles are usually male, and belong to different socio-economic backgrounds. He further explicated that online priming has five phases which are: formation of a friendship relationship, where the pedophile behaves in a friendly and kind way; formation of a relationship of trust, where the pedophile puts in place a whole series of techniques to demonstrate good faith and his honesty; assessment of the risk of being discovered, weighted by a series of protective attitude that encourages the minor; phase of the exclusive relationship where the pedophile promises personal advantages and favour perhaps of an economic nature and lastly the real sexual phase, where there is first physical contact. To this end, Seto, (2010) suggested that child pornography offenses can be considered as an indicator of pedophilia.

Further still, Ariana (2014) stated that easy access to social media platforms such as Facebook, Likee, Instagram, and TikTok, including internet-proliferated pornography, has also been identified as a potential contributing and/or identifying factor for pedophilia and sex offending. He further stated that research has indicated a correlation between child pornography viewing and engaging in child sexual abuse, although it is important to acknowledge that not all individuals who view child pornography engage in sexual abuse. The internet has helped in the proliferation of child pornography by

making it easily accessible and allowing viewers a way to maintain a certain degree of anonymity. He also claimed that the internet allows adults to engage in activities that are legal but inappropriate and might contribute to the etiology and progression of pedophilia (Murray, 2000, Andrews, Corry, Slade, Issakidis & Swanston, 2004).

Poverty: - Another significant contributive factor to the occurrence of pedophilia is poverty as noted by Shalini & Seema (2020). They think that child sexual abuse otherwise known as pedophilia is caused by poverty. Most of the cases of sexual abuse come from poor families where it is a trend to sell the child to fulfill daily needs. It should be stressed at this point that it is not that all cases of sexual abuse come only from the poor; some of them also come from the middle class and wealthy families. Poor and needy adolescents become victims of adult abusers, who pretend to help them but take advantage of them. Agbo (2019) submitted that due to economic recession and poverty in Nigeria, children especially girls hawk goods along the street as early as 6 or 7 years old to support their families and that most of these hawkers go nude or wear indecent dresses such as leggings or hanging tops that expose their little bodies as they hawk their wares around which unavoidably increase the chances of child rape – a form of pedophilia.

Rituals and occultism: - Some people also indulge in pedophilic acts not because they are naturally inclined to it as research reveals but just for rituals and occultism. Due to unemployment, acute economic recession and more especially high rate of materialism and Satanism in the country, many young men have sold their consciences to money, affluence and materialism. Agbo (2019) cited Nairaland Forum (2015) noted that some people believe that when women especially virgins

(children – adolescents) are raped, the destiny of the victim is transferred to the perpetrator through magical means. An example of this is when a pedophile used a white cloth to charm 11 children and abuse them sexually. He confessed that the act would reap the destiny of the victims spiritually to make him rich, but that he had not started being rich by the time he was caught. A man of 28 years in Osun state was also nabbed for defiling a 10-year-old girl, who used a leaf to wipe her private part after which she lost her consciousness and healthy physique. It was further revealed that this victim in reference was not his first dealing; he had slept with many young girls and he used to do so by laying a white piece of cloth down for his victims to lie on. (Opera News, March 2021).

Psychological and Health Effects of Pedophilia

Emotional and mental health problems: - Several mental health and emotional problems usually accompany pedophilia. Children who are sexually abused are at significantly greater risk for post-traumatic stress and other anxiety symptoms, depression and suicide attempts (Leeb, Lewis & Zolotor, 2011). Afolabi (2020) buttressed this stating that the immediate psychological consequences of child sexual abuse – pedophilia include shock, fear, anxiety, nervousness and guilt, symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder, denial, confusion, withdrawal, isolation and grief. Research has also found sexual abuse to be associated with several internalizing behaviours including anxiety, depression, problems with self-esteem, suicidal ideation and attempts, sleep disturbances, somatic complaints and fear of males (Hecht & Hansen, 1999). Kendell-Tackett, Williams and Finkelhor (1993) in Ciencia and Sauda (2017) observed that abused children displayed more psychological symptoms than non-abused children with

the most common symptoms being nightmares, depression, withdrawal behaviour, aggression, regressive behaviour and neurotic disorder.

However, insomnia as one of the effects can be explained by the presence of nightmares, fears and mood disorders such as depression while lack of friends and loneliness may be linked to aggressive behaviour or from the creation of new social bonds as well as being due to characteristics of low self – esteem and bullying. It should also be mentioned that the effects already commented on maybe even more serious if we consider the fact that psychological disorders can last a lifetime.

Guilt and shame: - Another consequential effect of pedophilia on adolescents is guilt and shame. In most cases, the abuser succeeds in convincing the victim that it is due to her own mistake, this thus leaves marks on the body and soul of the victim which makes her feel guilt and shame. She thus, finds it difficult to tell anyone about the abuse. Shalini and Seema (2020) added that the bad experience she received from that abuse compelled her to even commit suicide. The feeling of shame and guilt in some cases prevents adolescents from relating well with others, they always withdraw into their shells where they are supposed to enthusiastically interact with people around them. This leaves them depressed always as they are not courageous enough to disclose the incident to even their caregiver not to talk of teachers or counsellors that would assist them in handling the issue with little or no effects on their personality make-up and disposition.

On the above, Agbo (2019) subscribed that the victim of pedophilia has the greatest shame and stigmatization that may cost her self-esteem and self-image, especially in marriage. As long as people remember the incident, they may doubt her

health status including her fertility and ability to bear children, which may lead to her being rejected in marriage. Our society relies so much on moral beliefs, ethics and human etiquette, so when a child is sexually abused, it becomes a social stigma and makes the society lose its morality on the victim's life. The stigma may follow the pubescent/child to adulthood and become a hindrance to her marriage as not every man would like to marry a sexually assaulted victim for shame.

Forming and trusting relationship difficulty: - In addition to the above, pedophilia can cause difficulties in forming and trusting relationships. Afolabi (2020) noted that relationships can remind victims and survivors of sexual abuse and there may be emotional barriers that make it difficult to talk about sexual abuse partners. He further stressed that one of the most profound effects of child sexual abuse is the damaging impact it can have on the ability to form and maintain close, loving relationships – both intimate and platonic. It can affect the relationships that victims and survivors have at the time of the sexual abuse and for the rest of their lives. They may find it difficult to talk to partners, family and friends about sexual abuse, preventing others from being able to help and offer support.

Sexual behaviour problems and over-sexualized behaviour: -These are very common consequences of pedophilia on adolescent victims. Sexually abused victims appear to know more about sex and are more interested in sexual matters or genital regions. Hecht and Hansen (1999) in Seto (2019) buttressed this that heightened sexual activity, such as compulsive masturbation, precocious sexual play and overt sexual acting out towards adults and peers have been found among abused adolescents. Noll, Trickett and Putnam (2003) added that victims of

child sexual abuse are more likely to be sexually promiscuous. Stewart, Sebastiani, Delgado and Lopez (1996) in Shalini and Seema (2020) also mentioned unprotected sex, earlier sexual initiation, sex with multiple partners and an inability to negotiate and use contraceptives as some of the sexual behaviour problems exhibited by in-school adolescents resulting from the abuse they suffered.

Teenage pregnancy: - This is another menace associated with pedophilia. It is not uncommon in our society today that untold in-school girl adolescents that are out of school as a result of unwanted and unplanned pregnancies; this is a result of their being victims of pedophilia. Shalini & Seema (2020) said the risk of teen pregnancy is much higher for girls with a history of sexual abuse. They affirmed that the increased risk for pregnancy at a young age is likely due to over-sexualized behaviour which is a common consequence of child sexual abuse. Noll, Shenk, and Putnam (2009) also consented to this by stating that 45% of pregnant teens report a history of child sexual abuse. They also submitted that most sexual abuse incidents reported by pregnant teens occurred well before the incident that resulted in pregnancy. Reviews of teen pregnancies show that 50%-66% of adolescents who become mothers have a history of sexual abuse (Afolabi, 2020)

Life-terminating diseases and injury: - Sexually transmitted infections cum physical pains and injuries are other indelible effects of pedophilia on in-school adolescents. There is no gainsaying the fact that survivors of pedophilia are bound to be at risk of sexually transmitted diseases such as pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) which results from an untreated gonorrhea infection, genital herpes, syphilis, Chlamydia, HIV/AIDS, pubic lice and bacterial vaginosis (BV) to mention but a few. Any of these infections is capable of

jeopardizing one's life. Victims of pedophilia are at risk of these infectious diseases because of unprotected sexual relationships they suffer from predators who may be carriers of these infections and because they wouldn't want anybody to meet them in the act; no protection such as a condom would be used. They therefore directly transfer the disease into them and because of the fear, threats, guilt, shame, or stigmatization, the victims may not open up on time. The virus or bacteria transmitted in them would continue growing licentiously in them which may eventually terminate their lives after serious suffering.

Recommendations

The following are thus recommended to put the behaviour maladjustment under check:-

- i. There should be value-loaded education and enlightenment programmes to open the eyes of the public to the evils of pedophilia as it affects the adolescents, parents of the victims, the perpetrators, and society at large. Victims should be enlightened and educated through various prevention and intervention programmes on pedophilia, who pedophiles are? How they can protect themselves from being victims and as survivors how they can adjust and carry on with their life.
- ii. As home is the first school for all children, parents should endeavour to teach their children the right type of education to lay a solid foundation for education from other sources, so they say charity begins at home. Children should be taught assertive behaviours right from home so that they would be able to reject undue touching or advances from the opposite sex.
- iii. There should be advocacy for revitalization of the moral code and standard of the society, societal

norms and uprightness that always guide human behaviours in society at home, schools, religious places of worship and gatherings, on media both social and printed so much so that individuals would turn out to become well adjusted devoid of any behaviour disorder let alone pedophilia.

- iv. There should be reporting and disclosure of abuse cases to appropriate authorities so that the concerns are duly punished on the grounds of the nation's law and constitution, this would serve as a lesson and deterrent to other people nursing the same feeling to redirect their feelings from minors. In the same vein, the reporting should not only be done by either the victims or their parents alone, the medical practitioners should also report cases of sexual abuse that are brought to them to the appropriate authority for necessary legal actions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, from the review, it is discovered that pedophilia is a sexual disorder that has its origin in the moral laxity of the social system which makes fathers have canal knowledge of their daughter, teacher, pastor and alfa defiling children under their tutelage. This behaviour maladjustment is not so uncommon this day that it has found means of making itself regular amidst daily occurrence in our society has found out by this review and as irritating and embarrassing as it is, we have been conditioned to always hear one form or the other of it daily through our media, be it social or printed. This therefore calls for swift actions in checking and ameliorating the occurrences of pedophilia as it affects adolescents.

References

- Adedeji, B. O., Ezenagu, N. & Ajepe, I. F. (2019). "The Nigerian Girl-Child and Sexual Abuse: The Plight of Victims in Bayelsa State Nigeria" in *International Journal of Gender and Women's Studies*, 7(2), 123.
- Adegoke, A. A. (2016). *Adolescent and Adolescent Problems in Schools in Guidance and Counselling in Education*. Department of Counsellor Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. 19.
- Adekale, A. F. & Ajagbe, A. A. (2014). *Adolescent Psychology*. Ibadan, Association Publication Corporate Office. 7.
- Ademokoya, J. A. & Oyewumi, A. M. (2000). Informing the Deaf Adolescent About Sexually Transmitted Diseases in *Nigeria Journal of Applied Psychology*. Department of Guidance and Counselling, University of Ibadan. 99.
- Agbo, M. C. (2019). *Child Rape in Nigeria: Implications on the Education of the Child*. Retrieved from URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22158/ct.VZn1> . 13. January 30, 2019.
- Agbor, Timothy (2020). Girl Hospitalized after Rape in Osun as Court Remands Suspect. The Guidance Newspapers. (03 June, 2020). Guidance.ng/news/girl-hospitalized-after-rape-in-osun-as-court-remands-suspect/
- Afolabi, C.Y (2020). Child Sexual Abuse: Consequences and the Way Forward. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*. 8(6). 40-62, June 2020.
- Aina-Pelemo, A. D. (2021). *Nigerian Girl Child: The Socio-cultural and Legal Landscape of Paedophilic Activity*. *Journal of Commercial*

- and Property
Law.unizik.edu.ng/index-php/jcpl.
 ISSN:2736-0342.
- Akinade, E. A. (2022). *Developmental Psychology: A Life-span Approach*. Ibadan, Brightways Publishers. 71.
- Alutu, A. N. G (2017). *Theory and Practice of Guidance and Counselling*. 2nd ed. Benin City, Mindex Publishing Co. Ltd.
- American Psychiatric Association (2013). *Paraphilic Disorders: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (fifth edition; DSM-V), Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. American Psychiatric Publishing.
- Ariana, O. (2014). Examining Pedophilia: Causes, Treatments and the Effects of Stigmatization. International Centre for Missing & Exploited Children.
- Bridge, S. N. & Duman, N. (2018). Identifying Pedophilia in Life Skills. *Journal of Psychology*; 2(4), 215-222.
<http://www.researchgate.net/publication/321J12059>. Children and Teenagers. 2(1), 2019.
- Cohen, L. J. & Galynker, I. I. (2020). Clinical Features of Pedophilia and Implications for Treatment. In *Journal of Psychiatric Practice*, Beth Israel Medical Centre, New York.
- Doshi, S. M., Zanzrukiya, K. & Kumar, L. (2018). Paraphilic Infantilism, Diaperism and Pedophilia: A Review. *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine*, 56(4). Pp 12-15.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jflm.2018.02.026>.
- Durojaiye S. (2020). Hall of Shame: 23 States Yet to Pass Anti-rape Law, Majority are from The North. *International Centre for Investigative Reporting (ICIR)* Retrieved on 28th Sept.,2022 from www.icirnigeria.org/hall-of-shame-23-states-yet-to-pass-anti-rape-law-majority-are-from-the-north/
- Faturoti G. (2020). *Osun Arraigns Monarch, Son, One Other Over Alleged Child Sexual Abuse*. Retrieved on 28th Sept., 2022 from <https://independence.ng/osun-arraigns-monarch-son-other-over-alleged-child-rape-2/>
- Fontes, L. F. C., Conceicao, O. C. & Machado, S. (2017). Childhood and Adolescent Sexual Abuse, Victim Profile and Its Impact on Mental Health. *Ciencia&Saude Coletiva*, 22(9): 2919-2928, 2017.DOI:10.1590/1413-81232017229.11042017.
- Karolina G. (2018). Attitudes towards People with Pedophilia. Retrieved on 23rd May 2022 from <http://www.duo.dio.no>.
- Heather Cacciatori. (2017): *The Lived Experiences of Men Attracted to Minors and their Therapy-Seeking Behaviours*. Retrieved on 25 June 2022 from <http://scholarsworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations>
- Kawamoto, R. (2013). The Challenge of Studying Pedophilia. <https://digitalscholarship.univ.edu/award/14>.
- Leeb, R., Lewis, T. & Zolotar, A. J. (2011). A Review of Physical and Mental Health Consequences of Child Abuse and Neglect and Implications for Practice. *American Journal of Lifestyle Medicine*, 5(5), 454-468.
- Lizzy Bee Blog (2022). Chrisland School Saga. <https://topnaija.ng/chrisland-crisis-cctv-captured-what-really-happened-in-dubai-hotel/> Assessed on April 18, 2022.
- Lo Iacono, L., Trentini, C. and Carola, V. (2021). Psychological Consequences of Childhood Sexual Abuse :

- Current Knowledge and Clinical Implications. *Front Neurosci.* 15. 771511. Doi 103389/fnis.2021.771511
- Murray J.B. (2000). Psychological Profile of Pedophiles and Child Molesters. *The Journal of Psychology*, 134(2), 211-224.doi: 10.1080/00223980009600863.
- Nairaland Forum (2022). Case Study: Pedophilia/incestuous Acts on the Rise in Nigeria. Retrieved on 18th September, 2022 from <https://www.nairaland.com/1057232/case-study-p.aedophilia-incestuous-acts---/>
- Noll J.G, Trickett P.K & Putnam, F.W (2003). A Prospective Investigation of the Impact of Childhood Sexual Abuse on the Development of Sexuality. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 71, 575-586.
- Noll, J. G., Shenk, C., Barnes, J. E and Putnam, F. W (2009). Childhood Abuse, Avatar Choices and Other Risk Factors Associated With Internet-Initiated Victimization of Adolescent Girls. *Pediatrics* 123(6):e1078-83. Doi:10.1542/peds.2008-2983.
- Olusegun, O. O. & Idowu, A. A. (2016). Child Abuse in Nigeria: Dimension, Reasons for Its Persistence and Probable. *Child and Family Journal*:4:1(2).7ps//lawpublication sbarry.edu/cj/vol4/iss1/2.
- Oluwatosin, S.A & Akinbo, O.T. (2017). Prevalence and Perception on Causes of Pedophilia in Osun State. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal* 4(24) 103-110. URL:<http://dx.doi.org/10.14738/asrj.424.3847>.
- Perrotta, G. (2019). Paraphilic Disorder: Definition, Contexts and Clinical Strategies. *Journal of Addiction Neuro Research* 1:4. <https://bit.ly/2A97sVM>.
- Perrotta G. (2020). Pedophilia: Definition, Classifications, Criminological and Neurobiological Profiles and Clinical Treatment. A Complete Review. *Open Journal of Pediatrics and Child Health.* 5(1): 019 – 026. Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17352/ojpc.00026>.ISSN: 2640-7612.
- Punch (2018). Lagos Sexual Offences: Court Jails 58-year-old Paedophile for 60 years. Retrieved on 18th September, 2022 from <https://punchng.com/lagos-sexual-offences-court-jails-58-year-old-paedophile-for-60--/>
- Ripples Nigeria (2022). Court Sentences Baba Ijesha to 16 Years Imprisonment for Rape. Retrieved on 18th September, 2022 from <https://www.ripplesnigeria.com/just-in-court-sentences-baba-ijesha-to-16-years---/>
- Seto, M. C. (2004). Pedophilia and Sexual Offenses against Children. *Annual Review of Sex Research*, 15, 329 – 369. doi: 10.1080/10532528.2004.10559823.
- Seto, M. C. (2008). *Pedophilia and Offending against Children: Theory, Assessment and Intervention*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Seto, M. C. (2009). Pedophilia. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology.* 5, 391-407, Doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev.clinpsy.032408.153618>.
- Seto, M. C. (2018). *Pedophilia and Sexual Offending against Children: Theory, Assessment and Intervention.* 2nd Edition. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0000107-001>.
- Shalini Gupta & Seema Gorg. (2020):

- Causes and Effects of Child Sexual Abuse. DOI:10.38124/IJSRTZOM AY650. <http://ijisrt.com/causes-and-effects-of-child-sexual-abuse>.
- Strano, M. (2003). *Manuale di Crimilologia Clinica*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/380MOUa> on 28 July, 2022
- Tenbergen, G., Wittfoth, M., Frieling, H., Ponseti, J., Walter, M., Walter, H., ... & Kruger, T. H. (2015). The neurobiology and psychology of pedophilia: recent advances and challenges. *Frontiers in human neuroscience*, 9, 344.
- The Sun (2020). Rise of Pedophilia. Retrieved on 18th September, 2022 from <https://www.sunnewsonline.com/rise-of-pedophilia/>
- Vanguard Newspaper. (2016). 27year Old Man Arrested for Raping a 2year Old Girl. Retrieved from <https://vanguardngr.com-27-year-old---> on 28 Sept., 2021.
- Web News (2020). Osun Court Remands Man for Molesting 5 Year Old. Retrieved on 28th Sept., 2021 from <https://radionigeriaibadan.gov.ng/2020/09/29/osun-court-remands-man-for-molesting-5-year-old/>
- Williams, Mike (2019). "The NSPCC's Protect & Respect Child Sexual Exploitation Programme, A National Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Children (March 2021, retrieved).
- World Health Organization (2004). Child Sexual Abuse: A Silent Health Emergency, in Report Of the Regional Director. (AFR/RC54?15Rev.1, 2004). <<https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/1878/AFR.RC54.15%20Rev.1.pdf>.
- World Health Organization (2010). Pedophilia. International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems. 10th Revision (ICD-10) Version for 2010, Section F65.4.
- WHO (2016), March, 3). Report of the Consultation on Child Abuse Prevention. Geneva, Switzerland, <http://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/65900>.
- Yunus, N. M., Abu Yazid, Z. N., Abd Aziz, N. N., Ali, R. & Ahmad, S. H. (2018). A Conceptual Framework for Determinants of Paedophilia Crime. *International Journal for Studies on Children, Women, Elderly and Disabled*. 5(Oct.). ISSN0128 – 309X.